

RELIABILITY ESTIMATES OF FIELD HYDRAULIC CONDUCTIVITY OF COMPACTED LATERITIC SOILS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents results of reliability estimates of field hydraulic conductivity for compacted lateritic soils as landfill liners. The estimates were made by incorporating a predictive model for hydraulic conductivity, which was developed from field data, into a FORTRAN-based first-order reliability program. At any given reliability level, the estimated hydraulic conductivities decreased as compactor weight, plasticity index, or initial saturation increased. However, the hydraulic conductivities increased as either gravel content or clay content increased. The results also showed that, at any given value of each of the variables, hydraulic conductivity increased as the reliability or safety index increased. On the basis of the given mean values of initial saturation, clay content, and gravel content, it was shown that a realistic liner design can be made using only compactor weight and plasticity index, depending on a chosen reliability level. An example of a lateritic soil liner design has been presented for the case of a reliability index of 1.0.

KEYWORDS: Compaction, Compactor weight, Hydraulic conductivity, Lateritic soils Reliability analysis, Reliability index, Soil composition, Soil liners

INTRODUCTION

Compacted clay liners are an integral component of lining systems used for municipal and hazardous waste landfills (Benson and Trast, 1995). The hydraulic conductivity of clayey soil liners is required to be sufficiently low, usually less than 1×10^{-9} m/s, as the primary purpose of such compacted clay liners is to impede the flow of fluids. Hydraulic conductivity is taken as the basic parameter for design and for characterizing liner performance and reliability (Bogardi *et al.*, 1989).

The variability in the properties of lateritic soils in a given borrow site as well as from site to site is well documented in literatures (e.g. Gidigas 1980a, b; Ogunsanwo, 1985; Gidigas and Kuma, 1987). As with other soil types, these variabilities introduce uncertainties in engineering designs involving the use of lateritic soils. Hydraulic conductivity is one of the material properties of soils that are significantly affected by these variabilities in composition. Engineering analyses and designs require the application of probabilistic methods as deterministic approaches do not rigorously account for these uncertainties. Probability theory has been widely accepted and used in engineering. The application of probability theory to engineering analysis requires the knowledge of some statistical attributes of the relevant random variables such as their mean values and standard deviations (Kaymaz *et al.*, 1998). One of such probabilistic methods is reliability analysis which has been used in geoenvironmental engineering (e.g. Gilbert and Tang, 1995; Rowe and Fraser, 1995). Reliability analysis provides a frame work for establishing appropriate factors of safety and other design targets and leads to a better appreciation of the relative importance of uncertainties in different parameters (Christian and Baecher, 2001). Reliability analysis can be used to assess the suitability of compacted lateritic soils for use as liners and covers in waste containment structures.

This paper presents reliability estimates of field hydraulic conductivity of compacted lateritic soils. The first-order- reliability method was used in making estimates of hydraulic conductivity based on a predictive model developed from field data. The objectives of this study are:

1. To define hydraulic conductivities corresponding to different reliability levels for each of the variables shown to affect hydraulic conductivity; and
2. To estimate the hydraulic conductivities at a target reliability index value corresponding to certain compactor weights for given compaction conditions and a given borrow source.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Limit State Function

Soil liner reliability is defined as a probabilistic measure of assurance of post-construction performance characterized by hydraulic conductivity k , and is represented as (Bogardi *et al.*, 1989):

$$R = P(k < k_o) \tag{1}$$

where k_o = the specified hydraulic conductivity limit such as 1×10^{-7} cm/s. In this case, it will be reasonable to assume a condition of vertical porous media flow through compacted soil material with no macro-pores or open flow paths (or flow channels).

Reliability assessments help to determine the probability that the compacted soil liner will not attain any of the known limit states likely to be violated throughout the useful life, or at least some specified design period, of the liners in the face of uncertainties as human error inputs, various environmental conditions, variations in material and engineering properties, as well as prediction of future events. This probability of survival is given as:

$$P_s = 1 - P_f \tag{2}$$

where P_s = probability of survival and P_f = probability of failure.

The performance function of a soil liner can be modeled in terms of certain basic random variables X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n , which must operate within certain limits for the liner to function satisfactorily. Values of X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n outside of these limits constitute the failure domain, and that surface within the n -dimensional space of basic variables X_i that divides values of these variables into the failure domain and the domain for adequate performance is called the failure surface (Ocholi 2000). A mathematical representation of this surface is known as the limit state equation (Ditlevsen 1981).

In the reliability analysis of compacted soil liners, “failure” may be defined as the event of a liner hydraulic conductivity equal to or greater than the specified regulatory maximum (that is, 1×10^{-7} cm/s), over a given period of time such as the design life. The reliability problem is then formulated in terms of a limit state function $g(\mathbf{X})$, where \mathbf{X} is a vector of random variables, and $g(\mathbf{X}) \leq 0$ denotes the region in which the threshold value is met or exceeded. Adequate performance of the liner is established when $g(\mathbf{X}) > 0$. The limit state surface is denoted as $g(\mathbf{X}) = 0$. Thus, for a threshold hydraulic conductivity, k_o , the limit state function can be formulated as

$$g(\mathbf{X}) = \ln k_o - \ln k_e \tag{3}$$

where k_e is the expected hydraulic conductivity.

If $\mathbf{X} = x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$, has a joint probability distribution function (pdf) given by

$$F_x(x) = P\left[\prod_{i=1}^n (X_i \leq x_i)\right] \tag{4}$$

the probability of failure (that is, the probability that the threshold value is exceeded), $P(k_e \geq k_o)$, is obtained by integrating the joint pdf in the region where $g(\mathbf{X}) \leq 0$

$$P[g(\mathbf{X}) \leq 0] = \int_{g(\mathbf{X}) \leq 0} f_x(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \tag{5}$$

where $f_x(\mathbf{x})$ is the joint probability density or distribution function (pdf) of \mathbf{x} and the n -fold integral is over the unsafe region. In practice, a direct numerical evaluation of the multifold integral is virtually impossible (Jang *et*

al., 1994) due to a lack of full probability information. Some approximate methods have been developed for evaluating the integral, including first-and-second-order reliability methods (FORM and SORM), simulation methods, and hybrid methods combining simulation with FORM and/or SORM (Jang *et al.*, 1994).

In FORM, the integral in Eq (5) is evaluated in standard normal space by transforming the random variables X into a set of uncorrelated standard normal variates. $\mathbf{U} = U(\mathbf{X})$, having the pdf (Jang *et al.*, 1994):

$$\phi_{n(u)} = (2\pi)^{-\frac{n}{2}} \exp(-\frac{1}{2}|\mathbf{u}|^2) \quad (6)$$

where n is the number of random variables. Eq(5) can then be written as:

$$P[G(\mathbf{u}) \leq 0] = \int_{G(\mathbf{u}) \leq 0} \phi_n(\mathbf{u}) d\mathbf{u} \quad (7)$$

where $G(\mathbf{u}) = g(x(\mathbf{u}))$ is the limit state function in the transformed space. The limit state surface is replaced by a tangent point \mathbf{u}^* and the distance from the origin, known as the reliability index, β , is given by the inner product

$$\beta = \alpha^* \cdot \mathbf{u}^* \quad (8)$$

where α^* is the unit normal at the design point directed toward the failure region. The first - order approximation of the probability of exceeding the regulatory maximum is (Jang *et al.*, 1994):

$$P_f = \Phi(-\beta) \quad (9)$$

where $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the standard cumulative normal probability and β is also known as (geometric) safety index.

Estimation of Hydraulic Conductivity Based on “FORM”

The limit state function of the form of Eq.(3) used in this study was incorporated into a FORTRAN-based program with which the reliability analysis was performed. In this case the expected hydraulic conductivity, $\ln k_e$, is represented as follows:

$$\ln k_e = -18.35 + \frac{894}{W} - 0.08PI - 2.87S_i + 0.32\sqrt{G} + 0.02C + \varepsilon \quad (10)$$

where k_e is in centimetres per second; W = compactor weight in kilonewtons; G = percent gravel; C = percent clay, and S_i = initial saturation (in decimal form and estimated with the use of $G_s = 2.7$). Eq. (10) is a prediction model based on field measurements developed by Benson *et al* (1994), using a stepwise regression procedure, for estimating hydraulic conductivity of soil liners. The partial - F 's for the variables in the model are compactor weight ($F = 59.7$), PI ($F = 50.1$), percentage gravel ($F = 13.8$), initial saturation ($F = 5.1$), and percentage clay ($F = 4.9$).

Table 1: Comparison of statistical characteristics of lateritic soils and liner soils

S/No	Soil property	Lateritic soils			Liner soils (Benson et al (1994))		
		Range (N)	Mean	Std. Dev.	Range (N)	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Liquid limit, %	23-69(53)	41.305	11.045	15-91(67)	45.105	18.072
2	Plastic limit,%	13-39.5(53)	24.447	6.456	8-34(67)	19.462	5.503
3	Plasticity index,%	4-34.9(53)	16.862	8.184	2-62(67)	25.642	14.143
4	Gravel content, %	0-59(33)	25.563	17.339	0-22.2(65)	2.388	3.534
5	Sand content,%	9-61.7(32)	37.811	12.723	0.0-39.4(65)	15.198	9.316
6	Fines content, %	11-100(50)	41.646	20.855	44.3-100(66)	81.882	12.380
7	Silt content, %	2-99.5(27)	21.162	23.345	16.5-65.7(65)	41.354	11.986
8	Clay content, %	0.5-60(34)	23.48	15.359	13.9-75.3(65)	40.492	15.170
9	Activity	0.33-1.67(31)	0.8291	0.3653	0.14-1.12(65)	0.618	0.182
10	Specific gravity	2.55-2.9(49)	2.718	0.075	2.7	NA	NA
11	Optimum water content, %	7-35(59)	14.556	5.398	-	NA	NA
12	Maximum dry unit wight, kN/m ³	13.28-22.46(60)	18.757	2.103	-	NA	NA
13	Compaction water content, %	-	NA	NA	10.2-38.1(59)	19.863	6.195
14	Compaction dry unit weight, kN/m ³	-	NA	NA	12.5-19.8(57)	16.846	1.845
15	Degree of initial saturation,%	69.09-121.74(55)	92.94.	12.842	77-104(56)	91.571	5.460

N - number of data points; NA - not available

Table 2: Initial input parameters for reliability analysis

S/No	Variables	Distribution type IV (1,i)	Mean EX(i)	Standard Deviation SX (i)	Coefficient of variation, (%)
1	k_o , maximum hydraulic conductivity	Lognormal (=3)	1×10^{-9} m/s	2.7×10^{-10}	27
2	W, compactor weight (sheepfoot rollers only) PI, plasticity index	Weibull (=9)	261.4kN	61.4kN	23.5
3	S_i , degree of initial saturation	Lognormal (=3) Lognormal (=3)	16.9%	8.2%	48.5
4	G, gravel content C, clay content	Normal (=2) Normal (=2)	92.9%	12.8%	13.8
5			25.6%	17.3%	67.5
6			23.5%	15.4%	65.4

Table 3 Probabilities of failure corresponding to selected target reliability index values

S/No	Target reliability index values, β_t	Probability of failure, P_f
1	0.5	0.3085
2	0.75	0.2266
3	1	0.1587
4	1.25	0.1056
5	1.5	0.0668
6	1.75	0.0401
7	2	0.0228
8	2.25	0.0122
9	2.5	0.0062

Database and Statistical Analysis

A database was compiled by extracting data on lateritic soils from published literature (e.g. Meireles, 1967; Ola, 1983; Ogunsanwo, 1993; Osinubi, 1998a, 1998b) spanning between 1967 and 1998 and from laboratory test results. The data from published literature cover lateritic soils occurring within and outside Africa.

The statistical characteristics of the soil composition and compaction variables for lateritic soils are shown in Table 1 together with the corresponding values for the soils that formed the basis of the development of Eq. (10) by Benson *et al* (1994). The two soil groups have comparable ranges of values for their properties but the mean values and standard deviations of these properties differ significantly in some cases. The initial saturation values for the lateritic soils were computed with the use of the actual specific gravity values.

Statistical Distributions of Variables

Hydraulic conductivity is usually assumed to be lognormally distributed (Harrop - Williams, 1985; Bogardi *et al.*, 1989; Benson, 1993). Although alternative distributions have been proposed by Harrop - Williams (1985) and Benson (1993), the two parameter lognormal distribution type was adopted here for hydraulic conductivity.

A Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) goodness-of-fit test on the lateritic soil material properties as well as on the compactor weight (sheepsfoot rollers only from Benson *et al.*, 1994) indicates that both plasticity index and degree of initial saturation are lognormally distributed, clay content and gravel percentage are normally distributed, while the compactor weight has a Weibull (extreme value Type III) distribution. The distribution type for each variable as stated above was used in this study, although there are also some alternative distribution types.

Set-up of Numerical Experiments

The initial input parameters in the reliability analysis using FORM 5 (Gollwitzer *et al.*, 1988) are shown in Table 2. The numbers in brackets in column 3 of Table 2 are the various code numbers for the statistical distributions of the variables as used in FORM 5. The regulatory maximum hydraulic conductivity of 1×10^{-9} m/s for soil liners was set as the upper limit of hydraulic conductivity values and 1×10^{-12} m/s as the lower limit. The standard deviation of 2.7×10^{-10} m/s used in this study is based on values in literature (see Benson, 1993; Benson *et al.*, 1994). Various values of target reliability index (β_t) with a minimum of 0.5 and at intervals of 0.25 were used. The probabilities of failure corresponding to the selected target reliability index values are shown in Table 3. For each β_t value selected, hydraulic conductivity values were estimated at various mean values of the independent variables in turn. The following procedure was employed in estimating the hydraulic conductivities: (1) Mean values and standard deviations as well as the probability distribution function for each variable were established (FORM 5 automatically calculates the coefficient of variation); a target reliability index was also selected from the range given above to obtain set of hydraulic conductivities. (2) Each time, a mean value of a variable was selected and its coefficient of variation varied while the coefficients of variation of other variable were kept constant. When the range of coefficients of variation was exhausted, a new target reliability index was chosen until the full set of β_t values was completely utilized. (3) Thereafter, other variables were selected in turn and the entire procedure was repeated to obtain hydraulic conductivity values. The FORTRAN-based program utilized Eq. (10) for estimating the hydraulic conductivity values. The assumed mean values for each run of the FORM program were selected and varied at regular number intervals within the ranges specified as follows: compactor weight (240 - 340 kN); plasticity index (10% - 70%); degree of initial saturation (70% - 120%); clay content (10% - 80) and gravel content (1% - 10%).

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Variation of Hydraulic Conductivity with Compactor Weight

The estimated values of hydraulic conductivity for each mean value of compactor weight are shown in Fig. 1 for different target β_t values ranging between 0.50 and 1.50. For a given β_t value, hydraulic conductivity decreases as compactor weight increases when other variables in Eq (10) are kept constant. In Fig. 1 and for design purposes, it is possible to select a target hydraulic conductivity based on chosen values of compactor weight and β_t value. For instance, the hydraulic conductivity corresponding to compactor weight of 230 kN and a β_t value of 1.0 is 5.37×10^{-10} m/s. Hydraulic conductivity values increase as the required β_t value increases for a given compactor weight. Hydraulic conductivity at a compactor weight of 338 kN increases from 2.46×10^{-10} m/s at β_t value of 0.5 to 9.50×10^{-10} m/s at a β_t value of 1.5. The corresponding increases in hydraulic conductivity values for a compactor weight of 340 kN are from 2.42×10^{-10} m/s to 9.28×10^{-10} m/s. The trend in the relationship between hydraulic conductivity and compactor weight is consistent with Eq. (10) and graphical plot by Benson *et al* (1994).

Fig. 1 Hydraulic conductivity versus compactor weight

Variation of Hydraulic Conductivity with Plasticity Index

Estimates of hydraulic conductivity at values of β_t ranging between 0.50 and 2.50 were made for various mean values of plasticity index. The compactor weight was set at mean value of 338 kN (the highest value for sheepfoot rollers from Benson et al (1994)). The relationship between hydraulic conductivity and plasticity index for various β_t values is shown in Fig. 2. Hydraulic conductivity decreased as plasticity index increased for a given value of β_t . For instance, at a $\beta_t = 1.0$, hydraulic conductivity decreased from 6.86×10^{-10} m/s at 10% plasticity index to 2.70×10^{-11} m/s at a plasticity index of 70%. However, for a given plasticity index, hydraulic conductivity increases as the β_t increased. Hydraulic conductivity increased from 1.08×10^{-10} m/s to 7.33×10^{-10} m/s as β_t increased from 0.5 to 1.75 at a plasticity index of 30%. EPA (1989) recommended this value of plasticity index (30%) as an upper limit for compacted soil liners because of construction difficulties in the field with soils of higher plasticity indices. The trend of decreasing hydraulic conductivity values as plasticity index increases is in agreement with the findings of Benson and Trast (1995) as well as Benson et al (1999).

The trend in Fig. 2 shows that hydraulic conductivities less than 7.0×10^{-10} m/s can be achieved at a reliability level of 1.0 when lateritic soils having the following parameters are used and compacted in the field, initial saturation = $92.9 \pm 12.8\%$; compactor weight = 338 ± 79.4 kN; clay content = $23.5 \pm 15.4\%$ and gravel content = $10 \pm 6.76\%$. In order to achieve the hydraulic conductivities observed here and the high initial saturation, field compaction must be carried out wet of the line of optimums. Benson et al (1994) showed that plasticity index of liner soils can have considerable influence on their geometric mean hydraulic conductivity. This influence is clearly demonstrated in Fig. 2.

riation of Hydraulic Conductivity with Initial Saturation

The estimated hydraulic conductivities are plotted against the degree of initial saturation as shown in Fig. 3. The plots are for target reliability index (β_t) values ranging between 0.50 and 1.75. For each mean value of degree of initial saturation the hydraulic conductivity increased as β_t value increased. For instance at 85% initial saturation hydraulic conductivity increased from 3.07×10^{-10} m/s to 7.85×10^{-10} m/s as β_t increased from 0.50 to 1.25. Moreover hydraulic conductivity decreased as initial saturation increased. It is evident from Fig.3 that even at an initial saturation of 70% and using a mean compactor weight of 338 kN, hydraulic conductivities less than 1×10^{-9} m/s can be achieved at reliability levels of up to 1.0. The trends here are consistent with the findings of Benson et al (1994) and Benson et al (1999).

Fig. 3 Hydraulic conductivity versus degree of saturation

Variation of Hydraulic Conductivity with Clay Content

Hydraulic conductivity values are plotted against clay content for β_t values ranging between 0.50 and 1.50 (Fig. 4). At any given clay content hydraulic conductivity also increases with increasing β_t values. The trends in Fig. 4 also show that hydraulic conductivities increase with increasing clay contents. This is expected since all other variables in Eq. (10) were held constant. Benson and Trast (1995) observed that increasing clay content while maintaining the same plasticity index suggests that the clay fraction is composed of less active minerals, which generally corresponds to higher hydraulic conductivity. The trend of increasing hydraulic conductivity as clay

content increases is also expected for lateritic soils that have clay-size fractions which are largely kaolinitic. However, when kaolinitic soils are considered together with more active clay soils, hydraulic conductivity decreases as clay content increases (see Benson *et al.*, 1994; Benson and Trast, 1995). The trend of increasing hydraulic conductivity as clay content increases is also suggested by Eq. (10).

Fig. 4 Hydraulic conductivity versus clay content

It was not possible to achieve hydraulic conductivities lower than or equal to 1×10^{-7} cm/s at reliability levels greater than 1.50 for increases in clay content. At a reliability index of 1.50, which represents a probability of failure of 6.68×10^{-2} , hydraulic conductivity increases from 7.01×10^{-10} m/s to 1.0×10^{-9} m/s for increases in clay content from 10% to 30%. The corresponding increases in hydraulic conductivity are from 3.30×10^{-10} m/s to 5.20×10^{-10} m/s at a reliability index of 1.0, which indicates that the probability of the expected hydraulic conductivity exceeding the threshold value is 1.587×10^{-1} .

Variation of Hydraulic Conductivity with Gravel Content

The graph of hydraulic conductivity versus gravel content at given reliability index values between 0.50 and 1.75 is shown in Fig. 5. It is seen from the figure that hydraulic conductivities increase with increases in gravel contents, at each reliability level. For instance, at a reliability level of 1.0, hydraulic conductivity increased non-linearly from 2.14×10^{-10} m/s at a gravel content of 1.0% to 4.46×10^{-10} m/s at a gravel content of 10.0%. The mean value and the standard deviation for gravel content from the database are 25.6% and 17.3%, respectively. The mean value was scaled down to 10% so as to conform with the maximum of 10% gravel content recommended for soil liners (see EPA 1989, Das 1998). The scaled-down mean value for gravel content was used in the entire program for the iterations to estimate hydraulic conductivities. The scaling down resulted in decreases in hydraulic conductivity values. At a reliability index of 0.50, hydraulic conductivities were 8.54×10^{-10} m/s and 6.77×10^{-10} m/s at compactor weights of 280 kN and 300 kN, respectively, before scaling down. After the scaling down, the corresponding hydraulic conductivities were 4.49×10^{-10} m/s and 3.55×10^{-10} m/s, respectively, when other variables were kept constant.

As demonstrated by Benson *et al.* (1994), gravel contents between 0.0 and 10.0% generally yielded hydraulic conductivity values less than 1×10^{-9} m/s. Laboratory compacted soils with higher gravel contents (up to 50 - 60%) can still yield acceptable low hydraulic conductivities (that is, $< 1 \times 10^{-9}$ m/s) (see Shelley and Daniel, 1993). However, in either case, hydraulic conductivity increases as gravel contents increase. The effect of gravel content on hydraulic conductivity is explained in terms of changes in the primary matrix governing the flow of fluids in a compacted soil, when the gravel contents exceed a certain threshold value. Below such a value, sufficient fines and clay particles are available to fill pores between gravel particles with low conductivity material (Benson *et al.*, 1994).

Fig. 5 Hydraulic conductivity versus gravel content

Reliability-Based Design of Lateritic Soil Liners

On the basis of high partial - Fs associated with compactor weight and the plasticity index in Eq. (10) - (F for compactor weight = 59.7 and F for plasticity index = 50.1) compared to the partial Fs for other variables, it is reasonable to examine the relationship between hydraulic conductivity and plasticity index at different compactor weights. An example of this kind of relationship is shown for lateritic soils at a reliability index of 1.0 in Fig. 6. It can be seen (see Fig. 6) that at a given clay content (23.5%), gravel content (10%) as well as degree of initial saturation (92.9), hydraulic conductivity decreases with increasing compactor weight for a fixed value of plasticity index. For instance, the hydraulic conductivity decreases from 7.97×10^{-10} m/s to 2.05×10^{-10} m/s as compactor weight increases from 240 kN to 340 kN at plasticity index of 30%. The trend of decreasing hydraulic conductivity as plasticity index increases for a fixed compactor weight as observed in Fig. 2 is also evident in Fig. 6. Hydraulic conductivity decreased from 8.30×10^{-10} m/s at plasticity index of 10% to 3.1×10^{-11} m/s at a plasticity index of 70% at a compactor weight of 320 kN. Similar trends were also observed for other compactor weights. The soil must, however, be compacted at water contents of between 2 and 4 percent points wet of optimum water content. Results of laboratory compaction and hydraulic conductivity tests can be used as guide for this purpose.

Fig. 6 Hydraulic conductivity versus plasticity index for beta = 1.0

A possible design methodology employing the relationship in Fig.6 will require a specification of the target hydraulic conductivity and a given value of compactor weight. Alternatively, once the plasticity indices of

selected liner soils are determined and a suitable compactor weight is selected, then a possible range of target hydraulic conductivities can be obtained. For instance, if the plasticity index of soils in a lateritic soil deposit varies between 30% and 40% and a compactor weight of 300 kN is selected, then the target hydraulic conductivities lie between 1.81×10^{-10} m/s and 3.14×10^{-10} m/s. In this case the design is at a reliability level of 1.0. Similar ranges also are obtained at other compactor weights. It is possible to develop relationships similar to the ones shown in Fig.6 for other reliability levels. Benson et al (1994) showed how various hydraulic conductivities can be achieved given the compactor weights and plasticity indices when a liner soil has a gravel content of 2%, clay content of 40% and an initial saturation of 0.85 (85%). However, they did not specify any reliability level for the graphical relationship they obtained. Soil liner design should be accompanied by a statement of the reliability of the design.

CONCLUSIONS

The first - order reliability method (FORM) has been used to make estimates of field hydraulic conductivity for compacted lateritic soils based on a predictive model developed from field data. The model relates field geometric mean hydraulic conductivity to compactor weight, plasticity index, initial saturation, clay content and gravel content. The results of the reliability estimates show clearly that, at any given reliability level (or β value), hydraulic conductivity decreases as compactor weight or plasticity index or initial saturation increases. However, hydraulic conductivities increase as either clay contents or gravel contents increase for any targeted reliability level. For a fixed value of any of the soil composition and compaction variables, hydraulic conductivity increases as the predefined reliability index increases. The least values of hydraulic conductivity were obtained, in each case, at a reliability index of 0.5.

It is possible to accomplish a reliability-based design of lateritic soil liners using hydraulic conductivity estimates only. Depending on the specified reliability level, target hydraulic conductivity values can be selected once the plasticity index values of the field soils are determined from laboratory tests and a given compactor weight is decided upon for use. An example of a liner design has been presented for the case of a reliability index of 1.0. A reliability index of 1.0 is the lowest value specified by the NKB Report (1978) for serviceability limit state design of structural components.

In practice, fine-grained lateritic soils whose properties have statistical characteristics similar to those of the soils that were used in developing the field-based model can be used for constructing soil liners and covers to landfills. However, the selection of compactor weight and laboratory measured plasticity index values should be based on a target reliability index of not less than 1.0. This is to ensure a reliable soil liner construction.

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